

OPEN SCIENCE DASHBOARDS

ASSESSMENT AGAINST
INDICATOR PRINCIPLES
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OUTLINE

This short report details an assessment of the initial release candidate of the PLOS Open Science Indicators dashboard against the PLOS OSI Principles and the Principles of Open Science Monitoring (OSMI Principles). It focuses on the dashboard implementation and does not assess the indicators themselves in any significant detail.

The PLOS OSI Principles were developed as part of the PLOS program on open science monitoring and underpin the design and use of the indicators developed by PLOS. The OSMI Principles were developed through a consensus approach with international input. The OSMI Principles are more conceptual and high level than the PLOS Principles which are embedded within the OSI project itself. The dashboard design was informed directly by the PLOS Principles while the OSMI Principles were consulted as a reference point.

The dashboard generally performs well against both sets of principles. Key design questions address the tension between user demand for comparisons and the risks of inappropriate use of indicators to construct rankings or comparisons out of context. Resolving these tensions involves compromises and the discussion of these compromises and the reasoning behind them is part of the value of creating and addressing these sets of principles.

BACKGROUND TO THE PRINCIPLES

PLOS Open Science Indicator Principles

The PLOS Open Science Indicator Principles (Hrynaszkiewicz and Kiermer, 2022) were developed as part of the initiation of the OSI project. They were used to inform the design of the indicators and the toolchain used to produce them. At the core of these principles is the aim “...for these indicators to help understand practice and to promote improvements, not to rank journals, institutions or individuals”. This has informed the release strategy for the indicator data including the choice to not release identifying information at the article level that would make it easy to create such ranks.

There are six principles described in the original preprint:

1. Align with established community definitions or approaches wherever possible
2. Measure what and how Open Science practices are being carried now (as opposed to focusing on aspirational or gold standards, an approach which might simply point to a lack of activity in many fields)
3. Ensure interoperability across diverse geographic and subject/discipline domain communities
4. Adopt an approach that is scalable (automatable) across large volumes of literature/research outputs
5. Outputs, in particular underlying data, of Open Science Indicators/Monitoring frameworks must be available openly
6. Use Open Science Indicators responsibly – to understand researchers needs and support improvements in practice, not to audit or rank for compliance.

For the dashboard the indicators were used primarily as provided, so the most relevant principles are those relating to the approach and design (3, 4, 6) as well as transparency and openness (principle 5). Principle 1 is also relevant where choices are to be made on categorisation and technical issues where community standards will be preferred.

The Principles of Open Science Monitoring

The UNESCO Open Science Recommendation, adopted in 2021, includes a mandate to track and monitor the implementation of Open Science. To address this the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research initially brought together a group of French experts (Université de Lorraine, Inria) to work on a proposal for common monitoring principles. This text served as a basis for a conference which gathered international experts at the Paris

UNESCO headquarters in December 2023 which led to the formation of the Open Science Monitoring Initiative (OSMI). OSMI and UNESCO then conducted an international consultation and revision process to develop the Principles of Open Science Monitoring.

The OSMI Principles have three main pillars: 1) relevance and significance, 2) transparency and reproducibility, and 3) self-assessment and responsible use. The first pillar is most directly relevant to the indicators themselves, focusing on relevance, methodological rigour and usability. The second and third pillar are more directly relevant to the design of the dashboard, addressing both the technical approaches used in dashboard production and the release of relevant information and transparency of those approaches, as well as the user experience and how it guides a user to responsible use of the dashboard and underlying indicators.

VALIDATION AND ASSESSMENT PROCESSES

While the OSMI Principles include an expectation of self-assessment and reflection (Item 3.1 “Monitoring initiatives should ideally regularly assess and publicly disclose their compliance with these Principles”) there currently exists no formalised process for assessment. In common with other relevant sets of Principles (POSI, FAIR, CARE) there is an expectation of self-assessment and an aspiration for a process of community monitoring through critique of these self assessments.

At the time of writing we are not aware of any existing self-assessments beyond the description of the design process for the PLOS OSIs and how this was informed by the PLOS Principles. We have taken a light weight approach, adapted in part from the self assessments related to the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructures (POSI) combining a high level self assessment against each stated principle in each set separately, supported by a general narrative reflection that combines elements of both sets of principles together.

ASSESSMENT AGAINST THE PRINCIPLES

Each aspect of the two sets of principles is assessed based on its specific relevance to the case of these dashboards, and performance against the assessment. The ratings are Low-Medium-High for relevance and Poor-Medium-Good for performance. The goal is to use language that encourages ongoing improvement rather than claims of success or completion. There is some commentary provided against each element. One specific challenge is to distinguish between the dashboard itself and the Open Science Indicators that underlie it. The emphasis in this assessment is on the dashboard.

THE PLOS OPEN SCIENCE INDICATOR PRINCIPLES

Principle	Relevance	Performance	Commentary
1. Align with established community definitions or approaches wherever possible	Low (for dashboard)	Good	Most relevant to the indicators themselves. Standards have been adopted where available including ISO 3166-1 to identify countries and ROR to identify institutions and funders.
2. Measure what and how Open Science practices are being carried now	Low (for dashboard)	Medium	Most relevant to the indicators themselves which are focused on a specific context of open science practices which therefore has some limitations. Aspects of how different open science practices were categorized aimed to reflect the data and its divisions as they exist at the moment in practice.
3. Ensure interoperability across diverse geographic and subject/discipline domain communities	Medium	Medium	While the approach and analysis are interoperable and use general approaches there are limitations in the scope of the underlying data, mainly due to aspects of the indicators themselves and the scope of the OSI corpus. Expansion to capture a wider variety of output types and expressions of open science practice are technically highly challenging.
4. Adopt an approach that is scalable (automatable) across large volumes of literature/research outputs	High	Good	With the dashboard in place the data and analysis processes are capable of scaling to a very high level. In the longer term a very large corpus would require a different dashboard framework as the limitations of Looker Studio would mean the dashboard will be less

			responsive for a very large corpus. Other parts of the dashboard production process can be scaled to cover the entire literature.
5. Outputs, in particular underlying data, of Open Science Indicators/Monitoring frameworks must be available openly	High	Good	The underlying data, queries and code, processing and processed data are all available under an appropriate open license in appropriate repositories with industry standard metadata. The dashboard itself is built in Looker Studio which is a proprietary framework.
6. Use Open Science Indicators responsibly – to understand researchers needs and support improvements in practice, not to audit or rank for compliance.	High	Medium	The design of the dashboard focused on providing the capacity to make comparisons and draw conclusions but limited the capacity to create broad rankings (through limiting the number of available comparisons) or to focus on compliance of individual outputs (by not including data on individual outputs or authors)

THE PRINCIPLES OF OPEN SCIENCE MONITORING

Principle	Relevance	Performance	Commentary
1.1 Applicable and clear in scope	High	Medium	This relates primarily to the indicators themselves. Attention was paid to user flow and use patterns and to ensuring that the complex data elements were as clear as possible. Narrative support elements define scope and limitations.
1.2 Meaningful for planning and policy	High	Medium	User testing was conducted, specifically with organizational and funder stakeholders to identify use cases and design to support these. This is an area for future testing and refinement.
1.3 Co-created	Medium	Medium	The dashboard is a pilot project, to be seen in the context of the broader PLOS OSI program. A short period of user testing was conducted which informed design and the development process was collaborative.
1.4 Inclusive	High	Medium	The dashboard was designed to be comprehensive in its capability for coverage. The indicators are focused on elements

			<p>more relevant to STEM and the corpus is STEM focused. User testing was limited.</p> <p>Accessibility was addressed throughout the design process but a full accessibility audit has not been conducted for the pilot dashboard.</p>
1.5 Modular	Medium	Good	With respect to the data and analysis pipeline the parts of the dashboard framework are separable and a different dashboard implementation could be developed in the future. Looker Studio is a proprietary framework and while the design can be reused the specific dashboard construction is less re-usable.
1.6 Reliable	Medium	Medium	This element mainly relates to the indicators.
1.7 Consistent	High	Good	The analysis process is consistent across the corpus and all categories. While data representation may not be event (see 2.2 below) the processes implemented are consistent in their application.
2.1 Openness	High	Good (with caveats)	All data, code and other elements for the construction of the dashboard itself is made available. Looker Studio is not an open source product and there are therefore limitations on how the dashboards themselves can be shared, replicated or repurposed.
2.2 Quality of sources	High	Medium	The data sources used are documented. There are limitations in the coverage and accuracy of OpenAlex with known issues with affiliations and limitations to the coverage of funding information. This is one reason for not providing individual output information in the dashboard.
2.3 Public documentation of sources and methodology	High	Good	The full process code is released and a description of the analysis and data manipulations is provided, alongside the description of the preparation of the indicators themselves.

2.4 Reproducibility and reusability	High	Good	Data code and description are all made available.
2.5 Comprehensive metadata	High	Good	All resources made available in appropriate repositories providing industry standard metadata which is fully populated.
2.6 Consideration of community-defined and recognized principles	High	Good	The dashboard uses appropriate standards (ISO3609-1, ROR) and adopts recognized principles for reproducibility and description. There are limitations to the degree of community engagement in the process of design, although some user testing was conducted for this pilot.
2.7 Contextualized communication	High	Medium	Communication, description and design was developed to promote appropriate use of the dashboard and the indicators more broadly.
2.8 Disclosure of conflicts of interest	High	Good	Conflicts of interest are disclosed. PLOS is the primary developer and funder of the current OSI program.
3.1 Self-evaluation against the Principles of Open Science Monitoring	High	Good	A self assessment was conducted in this report.
3.2 Regular revision	Medium	To be confirmed	The current dashboard is a pilot and its performance and use will be assessed in the future. This may involve substantial revision or removal of the dashboard in the future.
3.3 Environmental responsibility	Medium	Medium	The dashboard process uses cloud computing and other approaches which is generally more energy efficient than local compute. No formal audit of energy use has been undertaken.
3.4 Long-term sustainability	Medium	Poor	The current dashboard is a pilot and is not planned for long term maintenance. The components (see 1.5 above) should be reusable in future projects.
3.5 Constructive comparison	High	Good	The design focused on allowing in context comparison across specific sets of organizations, funders or countries while

			limiting the capacity to generate simplistic rankings or large scale summary comparisons.
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GENERAL REFLECTION ON ASSESSMENT

The design of the dashboard focused on providing the capacity for comparison and analysis of the development of indicators over time, while not encouraging the use of large scale simple comparisons or rankings. As the underpinning data is available users may still generate their own rankings but the dashboard does not directly support this. This generally contributes to a good self assessment against qualities of responsible research assessment broadly.

The dashboard is also built on a reproducible research basis, with data and processing code shared in full. General reproducibility and transparency elements therefore also score well. The choice to use Looker Studio, driven by ease of use, low costs and rapid iteration capacity creates some limitations. As the dashboard is intended as a pilot this is not a serious problem but points to areas for consideration in the design of future dashboards, particularly if the decision to utilise a new framework is taken.

As a pilot there was not an extended co-creation process. User testing and consultation was conducted but was not extensive (~15 respondents across a range of sectors and geographies, primarily in North America and Europe). Indeed the production of the dashboard is part of the broader consultation process and responses to it will be monitored.

Generally the areas of weaker performance against both sets of principles relate to the qualities of the indicators and the challenges of producing them at all. Monitoring open science practices in all their diversity remains a challenge. The PLOS OSIs have taken a pragmatic approach in identifying core areas to focus on, and establishing a baseline on aspects of open science that can be associated with specific publications.

In turn this makes the dashboard an analysis of publications, and of a specific corpus of publications. However the dashboard is not seeking to cover “Open Science” writ large but rather engage potential users of the indicators with an interest in specific practices. To that extent and as a pilot its performance against both sets of principles is encouraging and offers specific areas for future improvement.

REFERENCES

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